

Resource Management in Grid Computing: A Review

Isah Abdul Azeez and Safwana Haque

Dept. of Communication and Network Systems Engineering, Faculty of Engineering,
University Putra Malaysia, Malaysia.

Corresponding Author's Email: isahtek@yahoo.com

Abstract

As technology advances and the popularity and dependence on internet increases by the day, new ways of finding faster and cheaper solutions to computational problems are sought. This has led to the development of a new concept known as grid computing, which is a type of distributed computing, heterogeneous in nature because it makes an aggregated use of resources distributed over a large geographical area to solve problems usually complex ones on a larger scale. Since it involves using resources from different places, from different ownerships and with different individual qualities, it requires a complex resource management process for its proper functioning. This article provides a brief overview on grid computing and its resource management processes, important factors considered in resource management, comparison of different resource management processes and future outlook of grid computing and its resource management.

Keywords: Distributed Systems, Grid Computing, Resource Management.

Introduction

Grid computing is an integrated computer network linking large geographically distributed and heterogeneous computer systems and resources, which eliminates the need for dedicated servers for job computations but uses distributive resources collectively to enhance computational power. It is a type of distributed computing different from other types like cloud computing and cluster computing. In this case, the resources are scattered over a wide span of area belonging to different individuals or companies, which are used to solve different segments of one single problem whose solution is gotten only after combining all the individual solutions of the segments computed by the different allocated resources. Instead of using dedicated resources from only one individual/organisation for computational purposes, grid provides a platform that enables resources from different organisations to be shared so as to enable problems to be solved according to the demand of the users. This helps in reducing costs, increasing the computational speed, efficiency, flexibility, scalability and performance. Examples of some resources that can be shared in grid networks are storage devices, operating systems, communication devices, bandwidth, simulation, softwares etc. To handle the different resource tasks such as allocation, assignment, authentication, authorisation etc. efficiently there is need for a good resource management planning.

Generally, grids can broadly be classified into data grids, service and computational grids. They are briefly explained below.

- Data grids allow a single very large set of data or information to be segmented and stored on multiple storage devices as one memory storage may not be enough.
- Service grids provide applications for the proper functioning of the grid e.g. maintenance services, resource analysis, task scheduling, security etc.
- Computational grids use resources collectively from different sources to solve a single problem for example, using softwares from different servers to solve a particular problem.

Grid computing is a complex system as it has to consider issues like the heterogeneity of resources available on the grid, the requirements of the different applications on the grid, the number of users demanding for services and the number of providers for the services, reliability or security of the grid, demand patterns (i.e. the time and geographical areas where services are used most), service policies for different applications etc. To handle these complexities of grid and for proper resource management, some of the concepts taken into consideration are:

- Amount of resources available for use,
- The type of resource (e.g. if it is memory or bandwidth),
- Resource allocation or availability period (i.e. the amount of time the resource is assigned for a task or user),
- Attributes of the resources : the storage capacity of the memory available and the speed of the network etc.

Various works have been discussed in the next section of this paper that considered different design policies for managing grid resources. Some factors such as failure rate (the frequency or probability of a task not getting accomplished), waiting time (the amount of time a task has to wait before it is executed), resource utilization (the amount and period for which a resource is used) etc. have been taken into consideration by different researchers to evaluate the resource management procedures implemented in grid computing.

Brief Description of Resource Management Concepts

A grid-computing system makes use of computer resources from multiple administrative domains that are applied collectively to solve a problem that has demanding requirements such as a large amount of processing power, storage space, bandwidth etc. However, a more generalised and formal definition of a Grid system can be described as “a large-scale, geographically distributed, hardware and software infrastructure composed of heterogeneous networked resources owned and shared by multiple administrative organizations which are coordinated to provide transparent, dependable, pervasive and consistent computing support to a wide range of applications. These applications can perform distributed computing, high throughput computing, on-demand computing, data-intensive computing, collaborative computing or multimedia computing” (Bote-Lorenzo et al., 2004). From the definitions above, it can be clearly seen that the base of grid technology is the concept of resource sharing/management.

The term resource management in grid computing can be defined as those operations that control the way that grid resources and services are made available for use by entities like users, applications and services (Khanli and Analoui, 2008) to ensure efficient utilization of computer resources and for optimization performance of specific tasks. Due to the complexity, heterogeneity and dynamic nature of grid computing environments, resource management is faced with challenges making it a complex task to match the capabilities of available resources to the needs of the entities listed above (Khanli and Analoui, 2008; Yanbing Liu and Yi Jian, 2006).

Some grid resource classifications are storage resources, network resources, computational resources which have capabilities like storage capacity available on disk, bandwidth of network, processor speed (Hao T., 2008). To handle the wide variances in the software applications and hardwares used in grid environments over different forms of grid networks, a software known as middleware is used. One of the most important components of the middleware is the resource manager which handles resource selection and job scheduling (Foster, Roy and Sander, 2000; Yang, Bai and Qiu, 2007). Discovery of resources becomes more difficult when resources owned by many organizations having different resource management policies and cost models are distributed over a wide geographic area and are heterogeneous in nature. To handle these problems a number of different scheduling and resource management algorithms and methods have been developed and implemented.

Resource Manager: Middleware

Middleware, which does not have a unanimous definition (Aiken et al., 2000), can generally be described as a layer of software that handles the heterogeneous functions of a distributed system like in grids or clouds. It exists between the application and the underlying components such as the operating system, networks and hardware, connecting them together and creating a useful environment. There are a number of different grid middleware kits such as Globus toolkit, ARC, gLite, UNICORE etc.

gLite is based on a two-level scheduling scheme; a central scheduler and a local scheduler (Laure et al., 2006). The two schedulers differ in that the central one decides which resources under different administration are assigned which tasks while the local scheduler selects exactly which task is executed by which resource. The schedulers are provided information to help make decisions by some components such as workload management system, monitoring and discovery service, file and replica catalogue service. Information about static and dynamic properties of grid environments are tracked such as number of tasks being executed, in which resources, how much is used. Dynamic parameters must be updated intermittently to ensure that the system functions efficiently and correctly as they keep changing with time. In KoDavis middleware, data is fragmented and stored in different site locations instead of in one central location. Even though it is not necessary to have all the datasets at one location before execution of a task, (Kokkinos et al., 2011) shows that it is better and beneficial to have all the datasets transferred to the central location either before or concurrently as the task is executed.

Resource Discovery

As one of the key issues in a grid system is how to manage all the types of distributed resources for job executions, a mechanism should thus be provided by the grid infrastructure to discover the relevant resource for its corresponding requests. In relation to this, Buyya and Venugopal, (2005) pointed that one of the main

capabilities of a grid infrastructure is the need to support a resource discovery mechanism which in turn plays an important role in the management of grid resources. Supporting this notion, researches in previous works stated that "Trustworthiness is considered to be an indicator of the quality of an entity's services. It is used to predicate the future behavior of an entity. If an entity is considered to be trustworthy then this entity will possibly provide good services in future transactions" (Golbeck and Hendler, 2004; Shankar et al., 2004).

In the process of resource discovery, there are a number of things that need to be taken into consideration. For example, assuming that there is a task that needs to be executed and needs a resource that can be provided by a service provider in a grid system. For the successful communication between the task and the resource provider, certain things need to be considered such as protecting the data from the provider and delivering it safely to the requesting party ensuring at the same time that the integrity and secrecy of the data are maintained. Transactions as this are important to the success of a grid environment and as such granting requests from trustworthy providers would be beneficial to the grid system as this would significantly reduce endangering the integrity of the system (Karaoglanoglou and Karatza, 2011).

Researches have been carried out by various researchers taking into consideration the above notion in resource sharing environments (e.g. clouds, grids and p2p) such as sand-boxing (Chang et al., 2000), encryption (Schneier, 1996) and other access control and authentication techniques. The problem with these however is that they incur extra overhead affecting the overall performance of the grid system. To overcome the additional overhead and also to enhance the integrity of the grid system, the trust factor should be incorporated into the resource discovery decisions (Karaoglanoglou and Karatza, 2011).

A significant work has been carried out towards the direction of trusted grid computing (Song et al., 2005, 2006) focusing on the security implications that could arise in such systems, however research concerning management of trust in the context of resource discovery carried out in grid systems is limited. An approach for resource discovery that is worth mentioning is the matchmaking framework (Raman et al., 1998). It was designed to solve real problems in the deployment of a high throughput computing system known as condor. Many other researches have been carried out by various researches with modifications to the existing framework such as (Raman, 2001; Tangmunarunkit et al., 2003; Zhu et al., 2004; Tangpongprasit et al., 2005; Maheswaran and Krauter, 2000; Vidal et al., 2006; Castano et al., 2004; Karaoglanoglou and Karatza, 2008). In this framework, the requestors and the providers of the resources in the grid system advertise their characteristics; the matchmaking component finds a match between the advertisements and informs the relevant entities i.e. the requestors and the providers of the matches if found.

Recently, researches have been focused on two systems that are based on the same basic principle of operations. They are grid systems and P2P systems both of which are provide a resource-sharing environment. The main difference between them however, is that grids are used purposely to solve complex scientific problems while P2P systems are mainly used for file-sharing like the ones carried out very commonly on the internet. Since P2P systems are more commonly used and much more developed than grid environments, the existing protocols of P2P are developed and implemented for use in grid environments (Iamnitchi et al., 2002; Al-Dmour and Teahan, 2005; Ali et al., 2005; Talia et al., 2006; Basu et al., 2005; Zerfiridis and Karatza, 2003; Crespo and Garcia-Molina, 2002).

An important resource discovery approach is semantic communities (Li and Vuong, 2005; Zhu et al., 2005; Somasundaram et al., 2006). This is based on the concept that grid and human communities are made up of members engaged in sharing and communication of data and resources thereby sharing similar-interest policies and allowing community nodes to learn about one another without relying on a central meeting point. A P2P trust policy used in grids is the NICE trust model (Lee et al., 2003). In this model, after every interaction, a client-entity cookie is established stating the quality of the transaction to the server-entity. This signed cookie is used to prove its trustworthiness to the other entities in the grid system. PeerTrust is another P2P trust policy implemented in grids that considers the amount of satisfaction, number of interaction and the balance factor of trust among the peers (Xiong and Liu, 2002, 2003). The satisfaction level a peer attains from a service is directly proportional to the interactions other peers had with this peer, the better a peer carries its tasks out, the higher level of satisfaction it will attain from its interactions with other peers. Another model of peers is EigenTrust (Kamvar et al., 2003) which uses the global reputation and local reputation of peers. The global reputation of a peer is determined by the local reputation value assigned to it by other peers weighted by their global reputation i.e. a peer with higher global reputation is more trustworthy. This method prevents sabotage by malicious peer groups.

Resource discovery mechanisms in grid systems which make use of trust relationship between resource requestors and providers prevent malicious attempts in the environment and also reduce extra overhead in the already complex grid systems. An efficient trust based resource discovery mechanism ensures a safer

environment for communication; enhance quality of service (QoS) and also easier decision making for allocating resources between the requestors and providers.

Resource Allocation and Scheduling

As previously discussed, grid resources are distributed heterogeneously over a large geographical area to numerous users simultaneously. To manage the use of these resources and users properly, tasks need to be scheduled precisely and allocated the corresponding demanded resources accordingly. Grid is a dynamic system, which changes continuously with time as a result of a number of factors such as availability of new resources, system/resource failure, new requests, completion of an executing task etc. When any of these occurs, there is need for jobs to be rescheduled or re-allocation of resources for execution. Unlike the conventional problems faced in scheduling and resource allocation in dynamic systems and other distributed systems, this problem of dynamic changes is much more complex and challenging and thus the conventional methods cannot be used efficiently in this case. To tackle this problem, use of decentralised methods for task scheduling and resource allocation in grid is a suitable solution which manages the grid resources efficiently and also executes users' demands (Izakian et al., 2010).

The method that has recently come into focus in managing resources is the usage of market based methods for grid environments. It allows the regulation of supply and demand for resources providing an opportunity for resource owners to participate in the grid and provides options of trade-offs to users between deadline, budget and QoS (Buyya et al., 2002). This method which is known as a broker has two characteristics which are: it must provide the opportunity to resource requestors and consumers to make scheduling decisions and also to have the adequate incentives to remain and play in the market (Xiao et al., 2008). There are basically two categories of market based models that are applied in grid systems for resource management which are commodities models and auction models.

In auction models, the requestor and provider of resources act independently and agree privately on the selling price of the resources in demand while in commodity models, the providers of the resources specify the selling price of their resources and charge users according to the amount of resources used and the duration used. Auction model is used for resources that have no standard values and their prices depend on their supply and demand at a given time. Auction models are easier to implement as they don't need global price information and are decentralised (Buyya et al., 2002). Auctions can be classified into four groups depending on the interactions that occur between the requestors and providers, they are as follows:

- the ascending auction (English auction),
- the descending auction (Dutch auction),
- the first-price and second-price sealed auction, and
- the double auction.

Buyya et al. in 2002 used economic based concepts including commodity market, posted price modelling, contract net model, bargaining models etc. resource allocation. Economic based resource management systems have been investigated by several researchers (Buyya et al., 2002; Xiao et al., 2008; Huang and Qiu, 2007; Attanasio et al., 2006; Chao et al., 2002; Huang et al., 2008; Gomoluch and Schroeder, 2003; Reddy and Gupta, 2006; Das and Grosu, 2005; Abramson et al., 2002; Wolski et al., 2001; Stevens et al., 2009; Garg et al., 2009; Anthony and Jennings, 2003).

An example of a computational economy driven resource broker is Nimrod-G (Abramson et al., 2002) which manages grid resources. Nimrod-G supports a number of economic models such as commodities markets, spot markets, and contract net. Investigations on first-price auction, vickrey auction and double auction models were carried out by Kant and Grosu in 2004 to find out which of the models was the most suitable for grid system for resource allocation from a requester and provider's perspective. It was deduced that when a combination of risk-averse and risk neutral users is considered, first-price auction favours resources, vickery auction favours users while double auction favours both users and resources. To optimize the time and budget relationship in a grid environment, Reddy and Gupta carried out a research in 2006 to develop a sealed bid method. Gomoluch and Schroeder studied the double auction protocol in 2003 to analyse its performance in resource allocation and compared it to other protocols. They found that the double auction protocol surpasses the performance of the conventional round-robin protocol. Attanasio et al. in 2006 studied heuristic protocols and developed an auction model based on a progressive Lagrangean heuristic and compared it to centralised heuristic methods showing that their method was more efficient. Works have been carried out by (Das and Grosu, 2005) proposing a combinatorial auction based resource allocation protocol. This protocol allows users to bid prices for a combination of resources used or needed for the execution of a particular task.

There are many more works that have been carried out on advanced auction protocols for resource allocation and task scheduling. Huang and Qiu in 2007 proposed an advanced resource reservation using agents participating in multiple sequential auctions. This method uses cognitive agents that automatically adapts to the environment, exchanges private information and learns new experiences from their neighbouring networks. An approach based on macroeconomics was proposed by Huang et al. in 2008, which is well suited for service-oriented grids and provides overall benefit of the grid market as a whole. This method gives some resource allocation strategies based on macroeconomic principles; stating that the total profit of all service providers in a grid environment can be increased while reducing the failure rate of grid service requests and the inquiry/waiting time for resource consumers and at the same time getting a good load balance for the grid market. Several multi-cost algorithms were presented for joint scheduling of communication and computation of resources by tasks in a grid (Stevens et al., 2009). Multi-cost schemes for performing immediate reservations and selection of computational resources for task execution and path determination for routing grid data were also introduced in this work.

Three meta-heuristic scheduling algorithms to reduce and manage cost of execution and make span of user applications in grids were proposed by Stevens et al. in 2009 including a cost metric to handle the trade-off between execution time and cost of resource consumption. An incentive-based scheduling method to increase the success rate of task execution and minimization of fairness deviation among grid resources and services were postulated by Xiao et al. in 2008. This method was based on a peer-peer decentralised scheduling framework. Wolski et al. studied grid commerce and its computational economies for controlling resource allocation in computational grid environments in 2001 measuring the efficiency of resource allocation based on commodities market and auction models. A heuristic framework based on decision making using autonomous agents to solve the problem of bidding across multiple auctions with varying start and end times with varying grid protocols such as English, Dutch, and Vickrey auctions was developed by Anthony et al. in 2003. Fuzzy sets were introduced by He et al. in 2004 to implement bidding of grid resources in the case of English auctions. This was used to retrieve resources in multiple overlapping auctions and express trade-offs between goods and previously done neuro-fuzzy methods. It was also used to predict the expected closing price of auctions and to adapt to an agent's bidding strategy.

Recognition of existing resources in a grid environment are done dynamically by a broker and the selection and mapping of resources to the appropriate demanding task (Othman et al., 2003; Yokoo et al., 2001; Kant and Grosu, 2004). Grid systems may offer static information about resources such architecture of memory structure, processor speed/frequency, operating system used etc. as well as dynamic details like present workload of a resource, resource queue, tasks in execution etc. to the broker or scheduler. A broker makes allocation and scheduling decisions according to the information gathered from the grid system thereby making its resource recognition and selection decisions. An important aspect of resource selection is accessibility authorization but most broker systems ignore this, imposing an overload to the grid environment. To explain this further, consider a grid system which selects resources for a task without taking into account the accessibility authorization factor. When the resource is allocated for execution, the task recognizes and selects it but then may not have the authorization to use it, as such, the resource will have to be dropped wasting time and money and at the same time increasing the workload of the system. The grid will have to re-allocate and schedule new resources for the task but then the same process may keep reoccurring before a perfect match is finally found. For this reason, Izkian et al. in 2010 suggested implementation of other units to assist brokers allocate and recognise available resources.

As one of the main reasons for overload in grid systems is the inadequate attention given to the accessibility authorization before allocation of resources, researches have been carried out to tackle this problem. This problem occurs because resources are first identified and selected for allocation before the accessibility authorisation of the resources are analysed using a different security unit as reported by (Grimshaw and Wulf, 1997). Othman et al. in 2003, tried to introduce a fairly complete architecture for a grid broker. This architecture had the capabilities of resource allocation, monitoring of execution processes. However, its deficiency like many other broker system is that its inability to control accessibility authorization before resource selection. A work by Elmroth and Tordsson in the year 2005 presented a more comprehensive architecture on scheduling by using an additional five components to the broker system for the resource selection and allocation processes. Despite its good design, this system had shortcomings such as no accessibility controlling, no monitoring at execution time and no deadlock possibility checking for dynamic job requests.

Bertino et al. in 2004 suggested that the process of accessibility authorization be introduced in the resource recognition phase. This work however does not present comprehensively how the model could be used for a broker system or for task scheduling. Recent works have been carried out to produce comprehensive architectures. These systems introduced a component for accessibility authorisation before resources selection. This reduces the workload of reselecting new resources for task executions when previously selected ones get

rejected. Some systems such as the one developed by Afrash and Rahmani in 2008, allow migration from one resource to another in case of a failure or damage. This architecture also facilitates the advance reservation of resources for application programs. Although such reservation reduces the system speed, it however increases the execution of application programs in a given time.

The proper execution of performance oriented programs usually requires high QoS. Such quality of service could be guaranteed by proper configuration, appropriate reservation and allocation of corresponding resources. The reservation mechanism to ensure the availability of a program's resources is used at the beginning, and the relevant mechanism for resource allocation is used in request time. Chen Jing and Ling-fu introduced a novel resource management plan in the year 2006 that aggregates the reservation mechanism in a way that is able to manage the resources effectively and enhance the QoS consistent with the reservation strategies and enhance the QoS consistent with the reservation strategies.

Conclusion and Future Directions

Grid computing is an important tool that is used for both scientific and industrial purposes, which provides an environment with a high amount of resources for computational purposes to solve complex problems. These resources can be scientific instruments, storage devices, network bandwidth, sensors and processors which belong to different proprietary organisations. This paper carries out a survey on resource management of grid in recent years. Some crucial factors considered in a grid environment are resource allocation, task scheduling, resource management and security. All these issues are dependent on one another in one way or the other.

From the study of different researches carried out on this field, the following conclusions have been deduced. Grid is a new field and has not been exploited or developed fully. Even though there have been numerous efforts to enhance the efficiency of distributed systems like grids, there are still many challenges in overcoming problems in managing grid resources. Various requirements and issues have to be handled such as conflicts between user requirements and resource providers. Grid systems are not so commonly used by common people as a result of poor awareness and also resource providers need to be given greater incentives to encourage sharing of more and reliable resources. Co-allocation of resources for multi-site applications or workflow is concerned by many people i.e. communication between two or more grid systems (inter-grid interaction) efficiently but that is only possible when intra-grid communication is perfected further. Also there is need for proper task scheduling to prevent loss of time and money and enabling efficient handling of resource transfer from one task to another, also allowing a task to use multiple resources concurrently and keeping track of all the activities in the grid without making the system slow and inefficient. Fairness in handling resource allocation to tasks according to the requirements should also be considered as an important issue and be developed further along with economic marketing methods to improve monetary values of resource management in grids.

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